

HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP GENERATION OF PRESERVATION METADATA FOR RESEARCH DATASET SEGMENTS

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Abstract – We propose a human-in-the-loop method for generating preservation metadata for research dataset segments using a conversational GPT-based assistant. Through interactive prompts, the agent engages users in documenting the content, provenance, and context of individual files. The method outputs both a human-readable markdown summary and a METS v2-compliant metadata package with embedded JPCOAR2-style descriptions. By integrating metadata creation into the research workflow itself, this approach lowers the barrier to producing submission-ready information packages while preserving interpretive and contextual knowledge essential for long-term access.

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I. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

In long-term digital preservation, metadata generation is essential but often burdensome, especially when researchers are responsible for describing their own outputs. Traditional Submission Information Packages (SIPs), as defined by the OAIS reference model, include content data and associated representation information. In practice, however, tools for preparing SIPs remain complex, and their use is limited outside formal archival pipelines.

At iPRES 2024, we argued for a bottom-up approach to research data preservation based on three key principles: (1) subdividing datasets into manageable, meaningful units—referred to in this work as *research data segments*; (2) embedding documentation as an integral part of the research workflow; and (3) embracing overlap or redundancy as valuable contextual glue. This perspective led to the need for a tool that helps researchers produce structured metadata for such segments—metadata that reflects not just what the data is, but how it came to be.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN AND WORKFLOW

We developed a custom GPT agent using OpenAI's GPTs framework, augmented with METS v2 as a structural packaging standard and JPCOAR2 as the descriptive metadata schema. The agent interacts with the user in a human-in-the-loop workflow to generate preservation metadata for each research dataset segment—a modular unit of data and documentation emerging from a discrete, well-scoped process. The workflow broadly follows these steps:

- Files are uploaded one by one, starting from the output of an individual research task or transformation.
- For each file, the agent prompts the user to describe its content, creation process, related sources, license, and relevant identifiers.
- When a file is known to have been generated via a script, the agent asks for its input files and the corresponding provenance path.
- After all uploads and explanations are complete, the agent outputs two files:
 - a mets.xml file using METS v2, with all metadata embedded via mdWrap sections
 - an index.md file summarizing the dataset segment in a human-readable format

The markdown document doubles as a conversational anchor: it is editable by the user and used to iteratively refine the mets.xml file. This fluid exchange between structured and narrative description reflects the dual role of metadata—as both machine-actionable and human-interpretable.

III. RELATION TO PRIOR WORK

Several recent studies have explored the use of GPT and other large language models (LLMs) for metadata creation in archives and libraries. The National Library Board of Singapore reported a 99.9% reduction in effort when using GPT-4o to generate metadata for archived websites, while highlighting the continued importance of human review for quality assurance [2]. The Library of Congress has also developed human-in-the-loop interfaces in which catalogers interactively refine AI-suggested subject terms and authority entries.

Across these efforts, a recurring theme is that AI can generate useful first drafts, but human intervention remains critical—a model echoed in our workflow. Our method goes further by capturing not only descriptions but also generation context and provenance, in line with the structure of SIPs and the provenance modeling principles of PREMIS.

IV. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

We tested the method with research dataset segments consisting of up to 20 files, including images, code, and text. In all cases, the GPT-based assistant successfully extracted JPCOAR2-compliant metadata and generated a valid METS v2 file,

requiring only minimal user input beyond simple descriptive explanations. License information, source URLs, and file-level provenance were also captured when prompted. A three-stage process emerged as effective: (1) file upload and dialogue, (2) metadata review and optional editing, and (3) final mets.xml export.

This work demonstrates how conversational AI can support the creation of SIP-level metadata packages for modular, well-scoped research outputs. By integrating markdown and METS v2 representations and enabling iterative clarification, the method reduces metadata friction while preserving human oversight. We invite attendees to explore the live agent at our poster and share their feedback on its potential use in diverse preservation contexts.

REFERENCES

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Akihiro Kameda is a researcher at the National Institutes for the Humanities (Japan), specializing in linked data, natural language processing, and research data management. His current work focuses on practical tools and methods for documenting research data in digital humanities.

